

Use of artificial intelligence in teaching and learning of Business education courses in tertiary institutions in Delta State

Ebierhoma Alex Ogheneovo¹, Ayo Oghenebrorhie Abel Ph.D²

1. *Business Education Department, College of Education Warri*
2. *Business Education Department, Delta State College of Education Mosogar*

Abstract

This study focused on the use of artificial intelligence in teaching and learning of business education courses in tertiary institutions in Delta State. Three research questions and three hypotheses guided the study. A descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study is 100 lecturers, and the sample size of the study was 48. An instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire. Data collected were analyzed using mean and standard deviation for the research questions, while t-test was used to analyze the hypotheses. The result from the study revealed that artificial intelligence can be used in teaching of accounting, office technology, management and marketing/purchasing education. Based on this, the study concluded that artificial intelligence, when fully harnessed, can be used to improve teaching and learning in tertiary institutions. The study recommended that Business educators should employ artificial intelligence in teaching accounting, office practice and skills to students of business education, Business educators should employ artificial intelligence in teaching office management and skills to students of business education and that Business educator should also employ artificial intelligence in teaching business management p and skills to students of business education

Keywords: Business Education, Artificial intelligence, Teaching and Learning, Office Technology

Introduction

Business Education is one of the technical and vocational education programmes in educational institutions aimed at impacting knowledge, skills and attitude to the recipients for self-development, job creation and employability. It aims at equipping its recipients with the necessary knowledge, skills and attitude that will enable the recipient to succeed in whatever business endeavour he/she may engaged in. Akume, (2018) defined Business Education as a programme designed to prepare individuals for gainful employment as semi-skilled workers in occupations that are not generally considered professional by the society. In the context of this study, business education is that part of the total educational process that provides the knowledge, skills, understanding and attitudes needed to perform in the business world as a producer and/or consumer. Furthermore, Business Education includes education for office occupation, accounting, distribution and marketing occupation, business, teaching, administration and economic understanding.

Business education is one of the courses offered in secondary school as Business Studies and in tertiary institutions. Courses such as bookkeeping, commerce, office practice, shorthand, and typewriting are taught as Business Studies in junior secondary schools. The philosophy and the objectives of business education, as contained in section 6, sub-section 49 of the National Policy on Education (2013), are to:

- i. provide the business knowledge and vocational skills necessary for industrial, commercial and economic development.
- ii. provide trained manpower in applied technology and commerce, particularly at sub-professional grades.
- iii. provide people who can apply scientific knowledge to the improvement and solution of economic and environmental

problems for the use and convenience of man.

- iv. enable our young men and women to have an intelligent understanding of the increasing complexity of technology.

Furthermore, Aina in Okereke (2024) posited that the objectives of Business Education broadly include:

- i. contribute to goal attainment of the total educational programme.
- ii. provide basic and business knowledge for all students
- iii. develop their economic understanding, personal consumer competency and personal-use competency; and
- iv. provide vocational skills for persons preparing for a business occupation, i.e. business competency.

Akinola in Maduka (2021) identified the objectives of Business Education as to:

1. prepare students for employment after graduation;
2. meet the manpower needs of the society;
3. increase the options available to each student and serving as motivation in order to enhance all types of learning;
4. present a laboratory in which practice skill, knowledge and attitude are learnt to make the classroom instruction more meaningful and relevant;
5. provide an opportunity through the use of local business for the student to acquire additional skills and knowledge;
6. give the students background of training this will contribute to rapid advancement on the job;
7. make students' development of such personality traits as punctuality,

dependability, accuracy, for effective and good sense of responsibility that makes for effective work;

8. help develop the right attitude towards and the habit of mind conducive to the proper use of technology;
9. provide the knowledge and skill necessary for industrial, commercial and economic development; provide people who can apply scientific knowledge to the improvement, solution and convenience of man;
10. give training, and impart the necessary skills leading to the promotion of craftsmanship, technicians and other skilled personnel who will be encourage creativity and to enable young men and women to have an intelligent understanding of the increasing complexity of technology; and
11. stimulate and encourage creativity and to enable young men and women to have an intelligent understanding of the increasing complexity of technology.

Ikpe (2013) further noted that generally accepted and defensible long range aims and objectives for Business Education are to:

1. equip the business students with the capacity to solve practical problems;
2. give the business students the capacity to communicate effectively both verbally and in writing;
3. provide the business students with a detailed knowledge of the intricate performance of a complex economic system; and
4. afford him/her through understanding of the functional arrears of business.

Scope wise, business education covers many areas such as Accounting, Management, Marketing and Office Technology and Management (OTM). Accounting education, for example involves the teaching of skills,

attitudes, competes and knowledge necessary to secure and pursue a successful teaching, business and/or accounting career. Osuala in Okorie (2021) opined that accounting education serves as character modifier, trainer and brightener of the innate abilities of those willing to attain economic independence and self-actualization. On their part, Ekwe and Abuka (2014) saw it as that aspect of study poised to impact the learners with needed knowledge, skills, attitude and competes necessary for ready employment. Traditionally, the primary objectives of accounting education curriculum include; to train Nigerian students for employment within a range of careers which include but not restricted to purchasing clerks, book keepers, payroll clerks, audit clerks, cashiering as well as business teachers involved in teaching accounting and allied subjects (Ezeani, 2012; Udo, 2014). Based on this, accounting education in tertiary institutions and the universities calls for the integration of instructional programmes tailored to educate and impart graduates to become intellectually versatile and adaptable to myriads of roles in which they may be called upon to perform in employment (Amao, 2018).

Management education on the other hand is a two-fold course of study offered as an option in business education programme. It combines “business/marketing management” and “education” disciplines. Considering them separately, one would not be wrong to assert that one of the most important and demanding activity in any organization be it public or private is management so far as there are predetermined aims and objectives to be achieved. The amalgamation of these two concepts produces Management Education. The tertiary institutions management education curriculum content set out as cited by

Okoroafor (2019) prescribes the teaching and learning of administrative office management, economics of production, organizational behaviour, small scale business management, human relations, human resources management, business organization and administration of business education as core courses alongside general courses and others in education. This in-use curriculum contents is expected to implant in the graduates’ employability skills. Thus, graduates of Business education employed in schools earn the onerous responsibility of discharging managerial functions which include management of infrastructure and facilities, classroom management, management of staff, equipment management, open space management, supplies management and financial resources management. Those employed in organizations other than schools could be involved in production management, distribution management and personnel management (Nwokoro, 2018). Other areas are procurement management, sales management, inventory management, event management, marketing management and so on.

Furthermore, marketing education is a programme of pedagogy in marketing mercantilism and management corned with training for the purpose of updating, upgrading, career development and operational management. Ehiamentalor in Ben, (2010) classified marketing education as one of the executive options in business education with a scintillating prospect for its graduates. Upon graduation, it is probable that graduates of this option of study can be employed to occupy teaching and leadership positions in secondary schools, technical colleges, tertiary institutions and other business-oriented outfits. Besides, they may be employed in ministries, agencies

and parastatals of the public service including industries, banks, or float their own businesses.

Finally, office Technology and Management Education (OTM) formerly known as Secretarial Studies is an integral part of vocational and technical education in tertiary institutions where emphasis is placed on the acquisition of skills for national development. The National Policy on Education (2014) defined Office Technology and Management as an aspect of education which prepares students towards the acquisition of practical and applied skills as well as basic scientific knowledge needed to perform adequately in the world of work. In other words, the programme is focused on the production of manpower that would be self-reliant and contribute to national and manpower development. Komolafe in Ajayi, (2010) described Office Technology and Management (OTM) as work-oriented educational programme which aims at skills acquisition for paid employment, self-reliance or employer of labour. Orija, (2012) described Office Technology and Management (OTM) as a specialized course of study designed to produce manpower of different cadres (with ND/ and HND qualifications) that will maintain and sustain offices in both private and public organisations. Office Technology and Management is the study of a wide range of subjects related to careers in the modern office of today. This programme provides the ability/training necessary to perform successfully in the many and varied clerical, secretarial and office administrative position.

From the foregoing, business education can be seen as a skill-oriented programme in tertiary institutions in Nigeria which aims to produce well qualified and competent graduates in business subjects as well as be able to teach business subjects in our secondary

schools and other related educational institutions.

However, in order to actualise the above aims of Tertiary institutions in Nigeria, there is need for adequate utilisation of effective innovation strategies for effective teaching and learning of the course. Such innovation strategy is the adoption of artificial intelligence.

Artificial intelligence is the simulation of human intelligence processes by machines, especially computer systems. According to Azubuike, (2022), artificial intelligence (AI) refers to the ability of a digital computer or computer-controlled robot to perform tasks commonly associated with intelligent beings. The term is frequently applied to the project of developing systems endowed with the intellectual processes characteristic of humans, such as the ability to reason, discover meaning, generalize, or learn from past experience. Scout, (2024) also indicated that artificial intelligence (AI) technology allows computers and machines to simulate human intelligence and problem-solving tasks. In the context of this paper, artificial intelligence refers to devices and decision-making aids that rely on automated, data driven, or algorithmic learning procedures. The ideal characteristic of artificial intelligence is its ability to rationalize and take action to achieve a specific goal. Examples of AI applications include expert systems, natural language processing (NLP), speech recognition and machine vision. Artificial intelligence devices include; robotics, self-driving car, smart home, AI television, computer vision, digital assistants, chatbots, face recognition machines, natural language processing equipment, security management tool, smart lock among others.

Artificial intelligence can be applied to all social sectors of life, including manufacturing industries, business, education, healthcare, skills development among others (Ebeh, 2019). This study focused on the application of artificial intelligence in teaching and learning of business education courses in tertiary institutions in Delta State. In writing, artificial intelligence is one of the teaching tools that could be adopted by business educators in improving students writing skills, decision making skills

research skill and the general academic development of students. Softwares such as chat GPT Google AI among others have been adopted by researchers in improving their writing skills. Okoroafor and Nweze (2021) have also indicated that artificial intelligence can be used for educational development.

Despite the importance of artificial intelligence in skills and knowledge development of students in the educational system, it appears that most students of Business education are not aware of strategies of harnessing the benefits of this new technologies to improve their academic performance. Most of the students still see these new technologies as mundane while other are having phobia in adopting it for their academic and skills development. Worst still, most students do not know what artificial intelligence is all about and how it can be harnessed for self-skill development after graduation. It is based on this that the study evaluates the use of artificial intelligence in improving the teaching and learning of business education in tertiary institutions in Delta state.

Statement of the Problem

AI has proved helpful as it has had a positive influence on various aspects of human lives and has enhanced the quality of human life through the establishment of search engines like Google Search, interactive systems like Siri and Alexa, automobile productions like self-driving cars and creative tools like Chat GPT and AI art. Use of artificial intelligence has been seen as a new technology that could improve teaching and learning process especially in tertiary institutions globally.

Nevertheless, despite all the above-mentioned importance of utilizing various AI-based tools, lecturers in Nigerian tertiary institutions, including tertiary institutions

in Delta state seem not to have fully embracing these technologies in their teaching and learning process. However, be it as it may, one cannot out rightly say certainly that lecturers in tertiary institutions in Delta state are not effectively utilizing AI-based tools in teaching business education. On this note it is worthwhile to state that, the primary concern is to find out the use of artificial intelligence in teaching and learning of business education subjects in tertiary institutions in Delta State. Thus, the choice of this topic is imperative since most of the lecturers in tertiary institutions in the state might not be aware that artificial intelligence can be adopted in teaching and learning of business education subjects such as office management/secretarial, accounting and marketing.

Purpose of the study

The main purpose of the study is to evaluate the use of artificial intelligence teaching and learning of business education courses in tertiary institutions in Delta State. Specifically, the study sought to;

1. Find out the use Artificial intelligence (AI) in the teaching and learning of accounting in tertiary institutions in Delta state
2. Examine the use Artificial intelligence (AI) in the teaching and learning of office technology and management (OTM)/secretarial studies in tertiary institutions in Delta state
3. Ascertain the use of Artificial intelligence (AI) in teaching and learning of marketing/purchasing education in tertiary institutions in Delta state

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study

1. What are the use of Artificial intelligence (AI) in the teaching and learning of accounting in tertiary institutions in Delta state?
2. What are the use of Artificial intelligence (AI) in the teaching and learning of office technology and management (OTM)/secretarial studies in tertiary institutions in Delta state?
3. What are the use Artificial intelligence (AI) in teaching and learning of marketing/purchasing education in tertiary institutions in Delta state?

Hypotheses

1. There is significant difference between male and female business educators mean response on the use Artificial intelligence (AI) in the teaching and learning of accounting in tertiary institutions in Delta state
2. There is significant difference between male and female business educators mean response on the use of Artificial intelligence (AI) in the teaching and learning of accounting in tertiary institutions in Delta state
3. There is significant difference between male and female business educators mean response on the use of Artificial intelligence (AI) in teaching and learning of marketing/purchasing education in tertiary institutions in Delta state

Methodology

The study adopted descriptive survey research which involved gathering data through the use of questionnaire. The population of the study consisted of 48 business education lecturers from tertiary institutions in Delta state The study utilized a validated four-point scale questionnaire with a reliability of 0.78 Cronbach Alpha reliability coefficient. The researchers with the help of two research assistants administered and collected the instrument from the respondents. The data collected for the study were analysed using the arithmetic mean and standard deviation. Any item with a mean

rating of 2.50 or above was regarded as accepted while mean rating less than 2.50 was regarded as not accepted. For the hypotheses, any item with t-calculated value greater than critical value was rejected, otherwise the hypothesis of no significant difference was accepted.

Results

Research Question 1: What are the use of Artificial intelligence (AI) in the teaching and learning of accounting in tertiary institutions in Delta state?

Table 1: Mean rating of the use Artificial intelligence (AI) in the teaching and learning of accounting in tertiary institutions in Delta state

S/N	Uses of artificial intelligence in teaching and learning of accounting	\bar{x}	SD	Decision
1	Balancing of account,	3.12	0.78	Agree
2	Data organization, and analysis,	3.25	0.81	Agree
3	Financial recording	3.24	0.84	Agree
4	Determine expense and payroll processing,	3.18	0.79	Agree
5	Financial and asset reporting,	2.87	0.46	Agree
6	forecasting.	3.25	0.81	Agree
7	Interpreting financial statements,	3.18	0.79	Agree
8	Auditing	3.12	0.78	Agree
Grand Mean		3.02		

Table 1 showed the mean rating of the use Artificial intelligence (AI) in the teaching and

learning of accounting in tertiary institutions in Delta state. Data from the table revealed that the respondents agreed that artificial intelligence can be used in teaching and learning of balancing of account, data organization, and analysis, financial recording, determine expense and payroll processing, financial and asset reporting, forecasting interpreting financial statements and auditing. This is evidently shown in the mean scores of the items which were above 2.5 the criterion for acceptance.

Research Question 2: What are the use of Artificial intelligence (AI) in the teaching and learning of office technology and management (OTM)/secretarial studies in tertiary institutions in Delta state?

Table 2: Mean rating of the use Artificial intelligence (AI) in the teaching and learning of office technology and management (OTM)/secretarial studies in tertiary institutions in Delta state

S/N	Uses of AI in teaching and learning of office OTM	\bar{x}	SD	Decision
1	Teaching office communication,	3.33	0.83	Agree
2	Documenting memos and munities of the meetings	3.24	0.84	Agree
3	welcoming visitors,	3.12	0.78	Agree
4	dispatching timely reminders.	3.25	0.81	Agree
5	Receiving customers feed back	3.18	0.79	Agree
6	Filing and bookkeeping	3.25	0.81	Agree
7	Data recording and management	3.18	0.79	Agree
Grand mean		3.2		

Table 2 showed the mean rating of the use Artificial intelligence (AI) in the teaching and learning of office technology and management (OTM)/secretarial studies in tertiary institutions in Delta state. Results from the table showed that all the 7 items were with the mean scores above 2.5 the criterion for acceptance. This means that artificial intelligence can be used in teaching and learning of office technology and management (OTM)/secretarial studies.

Research Question 3: What are the use of Artificial intelligence (AI) in teaching and learning of marketing/purchasing education in tertiary institutions in Delta state?

Table 3: Mean rating of the use Artificial intelligence (AI) in teaching and learning of marketing/purchasing education in tertiary institutions in Delta state

S/N	Use of artificial intelligence in the reaching of marketing/purchasing education	\bar{x}	SD	Decision
16	Keep accurate financial records	3.25	0.81	Required
17	Find out sources of capital	3.18	0.79	Required
18	Collection of data on customer product preference	3.33	0.83	Required
19	Giving a detailed result on customers feedback	3.25	0.81	Required
20	Identifying new potential customers	3.33	0.83	Required
21	Determination of the future natural disaster	3.24	0.81	Required
22	Alerting business owners on impending financial risk	3.25	0.81	Required

23	Scheduling business owners on meeting with like minds	3.18	0.79	Required
24	Use of professionals like bankers, accountants, lawyers, insurance agents and advertising agents	3.25	0.81	Required
Grand Mean		3.25	1.12	Required

Table 3 showed the mean rating of the use artificial intelligence (AI) in teaching and learning of marketing/purchasing education in tertiary institutions in Delta state. Result from the table showed that items 16-24 were with the means scores of 3.25, 3.18, 3.33, 3.25, 3.33, 3.24, 3.25, 3.18 and 3.25 respectively. This means that all the items were accepted by the respondents as the use of the use artificial intelligence (AI) in teaching and learning of marketing/purchasing education in tertiary institutions in Delta state.

Hypotheses

There is significant difference between male and female business educators mean response on the use Artificial intelligence (AI) in the teaching and learning of accounting in tertiary institutions in Delta state

Table 4: t-test summary of the mean ratings of male and female Business educators mean response on the use Artificial intelligence (AI) in the teaching and learning of accounting in tertiary institutions in Delta state

Gender	N	Mean	Std. D	Df	t-cal	p-value	Decision
Male	27	3.261	.3660	47	.195	.659	Not Significant
Female	21	3.248	.3774				

Table 4 shows no significant difference in the mean ratings of both male and female business educators on the use of Artificial intelligence (AI) in the teaching and learning of accounting in tertiary institutions in Delta state as the t-cal is .195 and the p-value (.659) is greater than the

stipulated 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted. Thus, there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of mean ratings of male and female Business educators on the use Artificial intelligence (AI) in the teaching and learning of accounting in tertiary institutions in Delta state.

There is significant difference between male and female business educators mean response on the use Artificial intelligence (AI) in the teaching and learning of accounting in tertiary institutions in Delta state

Table 5: t-test summary of the mean ratings of male and female business educators mean response on the use Artificial intelligence (AI) in the teaching and learning of accounting in tertiary institutions in Delta state

Gender	N	Mean	Std. D	Df	t-cal	p-value	Decision
Male	27	3.186	.353	47	.100	.752	Not Significant
Female	21	3.186	.354				

Table 5 shows no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female business educators mean response on the use Artificial intelligence (AI) in the teaching and learning of accounting in tertiary institutions in Delta state as the t-cal is .100 and the p-value (.752) is greater than the stipulated 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted. Thus, there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female business educators on the use Artificial intelligence (AI) in the teaching and learning of accounting in tertiary institutions in Delta state

Hypothesis III

There is significant difference between male and female business educators mean response on the use Artificial intelligence (AI) in teaching

and learning of marketing/purchasing education in tertiary institutions in Delta state

Table 4: t-test summary of the mean ratings male and female business educators mean response on the use Artificial intelligence (AI) in teaching and learning of marketing/purchasing education in tertiary institutions in Delta state

Gender	N	Mean	Std. D	Df	t-cal	p-value	Decision
Male	27	3.067	.386	318	0.000	.994	Not Significant
Female	21	3.057	.389				

Result in Table 8 shows a calculated p-value of .994 which is greater than t-critical value of .000 at 318 degree of freedom and 0.05 level of significance. This means that there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of female business educators mean response on the use Artificial intelligence (AI) in teaching and learning of marketing/purchasing education in tertiary institutions in Delta state. The null hypothesis is therefore upheld.

Discussion of Findings

Table 1 showed the mean rating the use of Artificial intelligence (AI) in improving in teaching and learning of accounting in tertiary institutions in Delta Stae. Results from the table revealed that the respondents agreed that artificial intelligence can be used in in teaching balancing of account. Balancing of account refers to the process of ensuring that the debit and credit sides of an account are equal. According to Madu and Anih (2023) artificial intelligence is one of the modern information and communication tools required for teaching students how to balance account. This report is also in accordance with Akah (2022) who

reported that artificial intelligence can be used in teaching students’ mathematical calculation and balancing of account. The result from the table also reported that the respondents agreed that artificial intelligence can be used in teaching and learning of data organization, and analysis, financial recording, determine expense and payroll processing, financial and asset reporting, forecasting and interpreting financial statements. This result is in accordance with Onwa (2023) who noted that artificial intelligence can be used in teaching students how to teach students ways of making financial analysis. The result from the study further showed that the respondents agreed that artificial intelligence can be used in teaching students on how to determine expense and payroll processing, financial and asset reporting, forecasting, fraud detection and workflow automation. These results are in accordance with Orji (2018) who noted that artificial intelligence can be used in the management of offices. In support of the above, the hypothesis 1 indicated that there is no significant differences in the mean ratings of male and female Business educators mean response on the use Artificial intelligence (AI) in the teaching and learning of accounting in tertiary institutions in Delta state

Table 2 showed the mean rating of the use Artificial intelligence (AI) in the teaching and learning of office technology and management (OTM)/secretarial studies in tertiary institutions in Delta state. The result from the study revealed that can be used in office management in the following ways; coordinating appointments. In most business offices, appointments are given customers for business purposes. In most modern offices, customers appointments are booked using artificial intelligence. This result is in accordance of with

Onyemечи (2020) who noted that artificial intelligence can be used in teaching students various time management strategies. The result further revealed that the respondent agreed that artificial intelligence can be used in orchestrating meetings, welcoming visitors, dispatching timely reminders, receiving customers feed-back, filing and bookkeeping, data recording and management. These results are in accordance with Ekeh (2018) who noted that artificial intelligence can be used in teaching students modern office management techniques. the result from the study further revealed that there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female business educators on the use Artificial intelligence (AI) in the teaching and learning of accounting in tertiary institutions in Delta state. This means that both male and female business educators accepted the artificial intelligence are useful in teaching and learning of office technology management.

Furthermore, table 3 showed the Mean rating of the use Artificial intelligence (AI) in teaching and learning of marketing/purchasing education in tertiary institutions in Delta state. Result from the table revealed that the respondents agreed that artificial intelligence can be used in teaching students of business education how to keep accurate financial records, find out sources of capital, collection of data on customer product preference, giving a detailed result on customers feedback, identifying new potential customers, determination of the future natural disaster, alerting business owners on impending financial risk, scheduling business owners on meeting with like minds and how to use of professionals like bankers, accountants, lawyers, insurance agents and advertising agents. This means that artificial intelligence

can be used in equipping students with veritable skills for business management.

Conclusion

Artificial intelligence has the potential of revolutionalising every sector including the education sector by enhancing learning experiences, supporting teachers and offering more personalized learning opportunities for students. Thus, educators must be equipped with the knowledge and strategies they will need to use this new technology to improve the teaching and learning processes in order to equip students with necessary skills for employment and job creation after graduation. Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded concludes that artificial intelligent can be used in equipping students with skills in accounting, office management and business management.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made;

1. Business education lecturers should employ artificial intelligence in teaching accounting practices and skills to students of business education
2. . Business education lecturers should employ artificial intelligence in teaching office management practices and skills to students of business education
3. Business education lecturers should employ artificial intelligence in teaching business management practices and skills to students of business education

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